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D7.2 - PUBLIC PROJECT WEBSITE

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
HEU	Horizon Europe
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
CTECH	CiaoTech – PNO Group

1 INTRODUCTION

Deliverable D7.2 Public project website deals with the public website of the MEASURED project, developed by CTECH and launched at M3 (March 2023).

The website represents the main D&C tool of the project, as it will allow to spread news, events and updates related to MEASURED to keep informed and engaged the main stakeholders and general audience, and to archive all the public documents that will be produced in the frame of MEASURED, such as deliverables, newsletters, D&C materials, press releases, etc.

2 PUBLIC WEBSITE

A dedicated, user- and mobile-friendly website for the MEASURED project has been realized and developed by CTECH at M3 (March 2023).

The website is available in English at the URL www.measured-project.eu and it has been set up using WordPress as Content Management System.

The MEASURED website has been conceived as a strategic tool for D&C purposes, and it will play an essential role in making available to visitors project results and the latest developments.

This tool will allow to:

- Inform the public about the context and objectives of MEASURED.
- Update the stakeholders of the field with news, events and downloadable project public documents.
- Create a network with the other EU funded projects and initiatives that are working on related topics.
- Wide spread of project's activities and initiatives.
- Facility the uptake of the project outcomes.

Figure 1: MEASURED website homepage

The project website has been set up considering the EC guidelines for dissemination and dissemination; for this reason, the footer of each website page displays the EU flag and disclaimer stating that MEASURED is receiving funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme.

Figure 2:MEASURED website footer

The website will be regularly updated with short press releases, news and events in order to keep stakeholders updated about the project progresses.

3 WEBSITE STRUCTURE

Seven areas have been conceived for the website – as showed in figure 3 – to provide a comprehensive description of the MEASURED aim and objectives, the organizations involved in the project, the related initiatives and how to get in contact with the consortium.

Figure 3: MEASURED website menu

3.1 “ABOUT” PAGE

Structured in 3 subcategories, the “About” page provides information about MEASURED, its aim and target and the project workplan.

Figure 4: About page

3.2 “PARTNERS” PAGE

The ‘Partners’ page displays the logo of the 17 participants – 2 SMEs, 7 industries and 8 Universities/research centers – involved in the MEASURED project. A short description of each partner, its role within the project, the logo and link to the website is provided.

Figure 5: Partners page

3.3 “NEWS&PRESS” PAGE

In this page will be published news related to the project progresses, including consortium meeting, events participation, scientific and non-scientific publications released by the consortium, and insights on the technical results achieved in the frame of MEASURED.

Figure 6: News&Press page

3.4 “EVENTS” PAGE

In the ‘Events’ page will be collected relevant national and international events in line with the MEASURED scope that the consortium might find interest to join to present the project.

Figure 7: Events page

3.5 “DOWNLOADS” PAGE

The ‘Downloads’ page has been thought as an archive to collect all the public documents that will be realized for the project, including public deliverables, publications – both scientific and non-scientific articles, project newsletters and D&C materials.

Figure 8: Downloads page

3.6 “RELATED PROJECTS” PAGE

The ‘Related Projects’ page is entirely dedicated to the MEASURED *sister* projects: other EU funded collaborative projects and initiatives that are working on related topics with which the MEASURED consortium will organize joint D&C activities.

CTECH will support close cooperation and networking with existing relevant projects which will be analysed in Task 1.1 (starting from INNOMEM and MACBETH).

Networking activities will strengthen impacts and increase the outreach potential of MEASURED. Synergies will be found in joint exploitation of dissemination tools and services (i.e., web exchange, common events to stakeholders, joint webinars).

Figure 9: Related projects page

3.7 “CONTACT US” PAGE

In this page has been included a simple contact form to allow visitors to ask for more details about MEASURED directly to the consortium.

In addition, the information of the project coordinator are displayed.

Figure 10: Contact website page

4 CONCLUSIONS

The MEASURED project website has been conceived as a key tool for the project D&C strategy, as it will allow to keep informed and engaged stakeholder and wide audience by regularly spreading news about the project results and progress, to archive and make available for download all the public documents, to discover more about the organizations involved and to get in contact with the coordinator.